

Block chain for Healthcare Management Systems: A Survey on Interoperability and Security

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KEYWORDS

Block Chain ,
Healthcare Interoperability ,
Security ,
Smart Contracts ,
Model-Driven Engineering(Mde)

ABSTRACT

In recent years it has been shown that the secure exchange of medical information significantly benefits people's life quality, improving their care and treatment. The interoperability of the entire healthcare ecosystem is a constant challenge, and even more, with all the risks posed to the security of healthcare information. Block chain technology is emerging as one of the main alternatives when it comes to finding a balance in the healthcare ecosystem. However, the constant development of new Block chain technologies and the evolution of healthcare systems make it difficult to find established proposals. From an architectural point of view, the design of block chain-based solutions requires trade-offs e.g. security and interoperability. This paper focuses on two main objectives, in the first one, it was carried out a Systematic Literature Review for exploring architectural mechanisms used to support the interoperability and security of Block chain-based Health Management Systems. Taking into account of results, a series of scenarios were generated where these mechanisms can be used along with their context, issues, and various architectural concerns (interoperability and security). In the second objective, a high-level architecture and its validation were proposed through an experiment for the whole process of developing a Domain Specific Language, using the Model Driven Engineering methodology for specific Smart Contracts.

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's globalized world, where the percentage of universal health coverage is only 50%. It is necessary for

everyone to have access to quality health services (diagnosis, treatment, and prevention) in an efficient, safe, and transparent manner [1]. For this purpose,

technologies that increase the coverage and quality of hospital services are being developed every day, and without them, medical centers would be inefficient and lose credibility [2]. The large healthcare ecosystem includes several interconnected stakeholders with different and sometimes competing needs. The healthcare environment involves a high degree of comprehensive and reliable information exchange between stakeholders [3]. However, this information is highly fragmented and distributed in multiple non-integrated data storage systems, making it impossible to have adequate information to support the care process and decision-making. This occurs because each medical center manages health information in an isolated and centralized way, causing health personnel to have a small history of the patient's entire life, which leads to errors in diagnosis and treatment. Likewise, having centralized information presents multiple information risks. This is highlighted by [4], which mentions that healthcare is one of the sectors most vulnerable to cyber attacks. Denial-of-service (DoS) attacks can occur to indispose information, or a ransomware attack to hijack information, which in many cases cannot be recovered [5]. For these and other reasons, it is necessary to have mechanisms that contribute to achieving interoperability between the information systems that support the care processes [6]. In addition, security is an indispensable element for disseminating patients' medical records, since this task entails various risks that cause serious damage to reputation, insurance, and finances, among other factors in the healthcare ecosystem [7]. The healthcare field is a topic that is researched daily from different approaches, one of which is the relationship between *Block chain* (BC) technology and the management of *Health Management Systems* (HMS), with the idea of improving aspects such as interoperability, security, traceability, confidentiality and information integrity. BC was first introduced by Satoshi Nakamoto in a paper on Bitcoin [8]. Applications of BC have been studied in financial environments (where it began), as well as in other growing areas of ICT. Now, it is considered a mainstream technology, used in different industries and use cases, such as identity management, contracts, supply chain, insurance, healthcare, voting, etc. [9]. Cloud computing is a new way of delivering computing resources and services. Many managers and experts believe it can

improve healthcare services, benefit healthcare research, and change the face of healthcare information technology [10]. However, as with any innovation, cloud computing must be rigorously evaluated before widespread adoption. [10] demonstrate how the cloud facilitates the exchange of healthcare data between providers, helping each provider manage their data, providing a seamless way to exchange data, and providing a unified/comprehensive view of each patient's (scattered) health records. In other words, cloud computing can be used to interconnect different healthcare providers, and be used by providers to cope with any sudden or seasonal changes. Scenarios in which the cloud plays an important role are discussed in the Background (Section II) and in Synthesis and Discussion (Section VI) of this document. *Software architecture* is the result of several In today's globalized world, where the percentage of universal health coverage is only 50%. It is necessary for everyone to have access to quality health services (diagnosis, treatment, and prevention) in an efficient, safe, and transparent manner [1]. For this purpose, technologies that increase the coverage and quality of hospital services are being developed every day, and without them, medical centers would be inefficient and lose credibility [2]. The large healthcare ecosystem includes several interconnected stakeholders with different and sometimes competing needs. The healthcare environment involves a high degree of comprehensive and reliable information exchange between stakeholders [3]. However, this information is highly fragmented and distributed in multiple non-integrated data storage systems, making it impossible to have adequate information to support the care process and decision-making. This occurs because each medical center manages health information in an isolated and centralized way, causing health personnel to have a small history of the patient's entire life, which leads to errors in diagnosis and treatment. Likewise, having centralized information presents multiple information risks. This is highlighted by [4], which mentions that healthcare is one of the sectors most vulnerable to cyber attacks. Denial-of-service (DoS) attacks can occur to indispose information, or a ransomware attack to hijack information, which in many cases cannot be recovered [5]. For these and other reasons, it is necessary to have mechanisms that contribute to achieving interoperability between the information

systems that support the care processes [6]. In addition, security is an indispensable element for disseminating patients' medical records, since this task entails various risks that cause serious damage to reputation, insurance, and finances, among other factors in the healthcare ecosystem [7]. The healthcare field is a topic that is researched daily from different approaches, one of which is the relationship between *Blockchain* (BC) technology and the management of *Health Management Systems* (HMS), with the idea of improving aspects such as interoperability, security, traceability, confidentiality, and information integrity. BC was first introduced by Satoshi Nakamoto in a paper on Bitcoin [8]. Applications of BC have been studied in financial environments (where it began), as well as in other growing areas of ICT. Now, it is considered a mainstream technology, used in different industries and use cases, such as identity management, contracts, supply chain, insurance, healthcare, voting, etc. [9]. Cloud computing is a new way of delivering computing resources and services. Many managers and experts believe it can improve healthcare services, benefit healthcare research, and change the face of healthcare information technology [10]. However, as with any innovation, cloud computing must be rigorously evaluated before widespread adoption. [10] demonstrate how the cloud facilitates the exchange of healthcare data between providers, helping each provider manage their data, providing a seamless way to exchange data, and providing a unified/comprehensive view of each patient's (scattered) health records. In other words, cloud computing can be used to interconnect different healthcare providers, and be used by providers to cope with any sudden or seasonal changes. Scenarios in which the cloud plays an important role are discussed in the Background (Section II) and in Synthesis and Discussion (Section VI) of this document. *Software architecture* is the result of several

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

In this section, we provide the necessary background information.

2.1 BLOCKCHAIN

BCs are driving the development of multiple applications, such as in healthcare. ABC is a data structure consisting of an ordered sequence of batch

entries, called blocks. The blocks are linked using the hash1 of the immediately preceding record (Figure 1).

The above guarantees immutability. ABC is maintained by a set of decentralized nodes (peers), which store a copy of the entire chain. These nodes, acting in response to a consensus protocol, are presented in this chapter. In the works [31], [32], and [33], the fundamentals of the BC technology are mentioned in more detail.

2.2 TYPES OF BLOCKCHAIN

Currently, there are different types of BC each with unique capabilities and features that suit different needs. These types of BC are public, private, permission, and consortium [16].

1) PUBLIC BLOCKCHAINS

It is a public infrastructure network, i.e. anyone is free to join the network without permission. Network participants can view and even participate, in and validate transactions. The most commonly used infrastructures are Ethereum and Bitcoin. Public BCs are mostly those applications open to the general public, where full transparency and decentralization are required. In addition, they encourage network members, called "miners"; to check transactions to receive in return some rewards in the form of crypto currency.

2) PRIVATE BLOCKCHAINS

They allow previously invited participants some type of transaction or extra block creation work within it. They are created for organizations that seek to have limited and private access to records and thus keep them out of the public's reach.

3) AUTHORIZED BLOCKCHAINS

In these networks, restrictions are imposed on who can participate in the network and in which transactions. Participants will need an invitation or permission to join [23].

4) CONSORTIUM BLOCKCHAINS

Several organizations can share the responsibilities of maintaining a BC. These pre-selected organizations determine who can send transactions or access data. A consortium BC is ideal for businesses when all participants must be authorized and have a shared responsibility for the BC [23].

2.3 CONSENSUS MECHANISMS

For a BC to be useful, there must be some mechanism by which nodes can mutually add new blocks to the chain. There are several consensus mechanisms, the most commonly used are the following [16]:

1) PROOF OF WORK (PoW)

Process by which nodes compete to generate the next block by expending computational effort to solve a challenging mathematical problem (e.g., in Bitcoin). The first node arrives at a solution that transmits the result to the network; the 5632 solution is verified by the remaining nodes, the block is added to the chain, and then work begins on the next block [21].

2) PROOF OF STAKE

(PoS) PoS algorithms waive the computational challenge but offer only a randomly selected subset of nodes the opportunity to produce each block. The probability of selection is weighted according to each entity's existing level of investment in the system, typically quantified as the value or duration of asset holdings relevant to that particular BC [35].

3) PROOF OF DELEGATED PARTICIPATION

Those who hold the network token are able to cast votes to elect block producers; votes are weighted by the voter's stake, and the block producer candidates that receive the most votes are those who produce blocks. Users can also delegate ("proxy") their voting power to another user [36].

4) Practical Byzantine Fault Tolerance

This mechanism guarantees consensus despite the arbitrary behavior of the participants. A new block is added if more than two-thirds of all validation pairs propose the same response [37]. An important variant of this mechanism is discussed in [38], who propose a reputation-based Delegated Byzantine Fault Tolerance consensus (DBFT) algorithm to efficiently achieve consensus on the authoritative BC. Other less relevant consensus mechanisms used are Proof of Authority (PoA) [39], QuorumChain [40], Raft [41], among others. An in-depth study of consensus mechanisms can be found in [42].

2.4 BLOCKCHAIN PLATFORMS

The following is a description of the most commonly used BC platforms in healthcare environments:

1) ETHEREUM

Ethereum,² is an open-source platform to write and distribute decentralized applications and the first platform that supports advanced general-purpose SC (Turing-complete) whose primary language used in the BC is Solidity [43] and transactions are sent to Ethereum through Virtual Machine (EVM) to execute methods [44].

2) HYPERLEDGER FABRIC

Hyper ledger, ³ the open global eco system for enterprise-grade BC technologies. Is an open-source, enterprise-grade, per missioned distributed ledger technology (DLT) platform designed for use in enterprise contexts [45].

This project, called Fabric, has a highly modular and configurable architecture, enabling innovation, versatility, and optimization for a wide range of industry use cases, including banking, finance, insurance, healthcare, human resources, and supply chain.

3. EXISTING SYSTEM

To carry out this SLR, we followed the methodology defined by Petersen et al. [13] and Kitchenham and Brereton [12]. The main objective is to explore what architectural mechanisms are being used to support the interoperability and security of HMSs using BC. The SLR is divided into different sequential steps. The papers were analyzed and classified according to categories created to separate the research contributions of each paper (Results section IV). The data extracted from the papers were stored and subjected to qualitative and quantitative analysis. This analysis aimed to find evidence to answer the RQs defined in the Conducting Search section (III). To organize the findings and document the data extraction process, a spreadsheet was used, which also allowed other statistical analyzes to be carried out, such as determining the number of publications per year, by place, and by type, among other analyzes.

4. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In the proposed system to Present a Systematic Literature Review SLR, in which we identified and discussed BC interoperability and security solutions. We identify and classify papers to find architectural mechanisms used in healthcare environments that use BC and identify architectural elements that support solutions in these environments. Detail 7 scenarios, representing 7 ways to architecturally approach solutions using BC in healthcare. In each scenario, we present an overview, of the problem, analyze interoperability and security, and relate some security and interoperability tactics. We then discuss some trade-offs used to balance interoperability and security in the healthcare ecosystem using BC. We propose a MDE Framework for block chain interoperability and

security. This framework consists of a high-level architecture whose main objective is the development of a DSL for the specification of SC independent of the BC platform used, to contribute to the interoperability and security of the healthcare environment. We propose an experiment developed under the MDE methodology, to put this architecture in context and validate each of the elements required in this solution.

SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig 1: System Architecture

5. OUTPUT SCREENS

Fig.1 : User Home Page

In above screen shows the home page of the User.

Fig.2 : Health Care Login

In above screen shows the health care login page

Fig.3 : upload Patient Data

In above screen shows the all block chain datasets.

Fig.4: Admin Home Page

In above screen shows the Admin home page.

Fig.5 : Diseases results in Bar Chart Graph

In above screen shows the Diseases results in Bar Chart Graph.

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we conducted a Systematic Literature Review on mechanisms and architectural elements aimed at improving the interoperability and security of HMS using BC. We have systematically analyzed, compared, and discussed 21 papers, corresponding to the same number of interoperability and security solutions in the field of BC technology. By methodologically exploring each of the solutions, this

study provides interesting reflections, the first thing is to expose in a clear way the architectural mechanisms used to support solutions using BC in healthcare environments, among these are Frameworks, Gateways, Proxies, API, DSL's, MDE, among others. The second thing is to analyze, describe and classify architectural tactics used to solve interoperability and security concerns of HMS using BC. As a third point, we generate 7 high-level scenarios, which represent 7 ways to address the architectural level solutions using BC in the healthcare field, in each of these we describe its context, a problem, analyze interoperability and security concerns, and then describe and analyze some trade-offs used to balance the interoperability and security of the healthcare ecosystem using BC. As a fourth point, We present a MDE Framework for block chain interoperability and security. This framework consists of a high-level architecture that has as a central element the creation of a DSL that will be used for the translation of SC independently of the BC platform, to validate this architecture, we design an MDE experiment, which will allow us to validate the whole MDE process, This experiment seeks to look at the feasibility and determine if we are working at the right abstraction levels for the generation of SC between different BC platforms. In addition, it will allow us to make adjustments to the process and strengthen the components that are well-defined.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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